

Ohio Small Town Sustainability Survey 2016

Start of Block: Section I - Community Satisfaction

Q283

Q287 Welcome to the 2016 Ohio Small Town Sustainability Survey! We thank you for your interest in participating in the Ohio Small Town Sustainability Survey. To thank you for your participation, you will have a chance to win \$100!

As a reminder we ask that only one adult (age 18+) member of your household participate in the survey. Your household's participation in this survey is entirely voluntary and the information you provide will be used to help local organizations evaluate and better understand the opportunities and challenges in implementing local sustainability and energy use reduction initiatives in communities like yours. Please note that to continue to the survey you will need your RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the lower right-hand corner of the letter inviting you to participate. We thank you for taking the time to share your opinions and learn more about the survey. Sincerely, Cynthia Frantz Ph.D Professor of Psychology Oberlin College To continue to the next screen please click in the button marked ">>" on the bottom left corner of each screen. If you should lose your internet connection or wish to resume the survey where you left off, simply return to www.townsurvey.org

Page Break

Q77 Please enter the **RESPONDENT ID*** as indicated on the letter inviting you to participate. Please note that on the following screen you will have the option of participating or declining participation in the survey.

Q124 * The RESPONDENT ID is located on the lower right-hand portion of the letter inviting you to participate which also included the link to this survey web-site. Please note that the RESPONDENT ID assures that the final survey results do not include any duplicate entries from the same person or household and also assures that the information you provide in this survey today will at no time be linked to any personal identifying information

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Q113 OHIO SMALL TOWN SUSTAINABILITY SURVEY - 2016 Survey Information & Consent to Participate

This survey is part of a longitudinal study of community life in your town. The survey which follows will ask you for your opinions about life in your community as well as you and your household's use of electricity and other resources. The survey will take between 15 - 20 minutes to complete. Responses to this survey will be compared to a similar survey that was administered 4 years ago. To thank you for your time, you will have a chance to win \$100. Your household was randomly selected to participate in this survey based on a list of all residential addresses in your city. Unlike a Census which collects information from all households, the community survey is designed to get a representative sample of your city's population. This random selection process is essential to assure that the responses collected reflect the "average" responses of all community members and not just those who are most interested in participating. There are no known risks or discomforts involved in your participation in this survey. There are also no direct benefits to you or your household for participation. There may be certain common benefits to the community as a whole by helping to improve the quality of information available to local organizations. [L1L1] [SEP1SEP1] Your responses to this survey will be strictly confidential and your contact information, identity, address, phone number and any other identifying information will not be disclosed in the reporting of the results nor will it be directly linked to your responses. At no time will anyone be provided access to individual responses to this survey which could be used to identify an individual respondent. All results from the survey will be reported for the entire community and never on an individual basis nor in a way that would possibly identify you or anyone in your household.

You must be a 18 years of age or over to participate in this community survey. Your participation in this survey is strictly voluntary and declining participation or stopping participation at any time does not imply any form of penalty or loss of benefits, nor will it impact the delivery, quantity, quality or cost of any city services or utilities. Your household will be eligible to participate in future years of the survey even if you decline participation this year.

[L1L1] [SEP1SEP1] If you should have any question about your participation in this survey, please contact Dr. Cynthia Frantz, Professor of Psychology, at 440-775-8499 or at cindy.frantz@oberlin.edu. If you have any questions about your rights as a participant, please contact Pablo Mitchell, Chair of the Institutional Review Board at (440) 775-8410 or pablo.mitchell@oberlin.edu. We recommend that you print a copy of this page for your records.

- I hereby confirm that I am 18 years of age or older and have read and understood the statements and instructions above and give my consent to participate in the Ohio Small Town Sustainability Survey. (1)
- I would like to decline participation on behalf of myself and my household. (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If Q113 = I would like to decline participation on behalf of myself and my household.

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Q260 Please confirm that you are a current resident of city listed below by selecting the circle next to that city name.

Display This Choice:

If If Please enter the RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the ... Text Response Is Contains A*

Oberlin (1)

Display This Choice:

If If Please enter the RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the ... Text Response Is Contains B*

Berea (2)

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Q284 COMMUNITY SATISFACTION The first few questions are about your overall satisfaction with life in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement. Please note that throughout the survey " $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ " refers to the City of $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$.

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Q1 Overall, how satisfied are you with life in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}?

- Very Satisfied (1)
- Satisfied (2)
- Neutral (3)
- Dissatisfied (4)
- Very Dissatisfied (5)

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Q2 When thinking about life in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$, how satisfied are you with each of the following?

	Very Satisfied (1)	Satisfied (2)	Neutral (3)	Dissatisfied (4)	Very Dissatisfied (5)
Retail and shopping opportunities (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Employment opportunities (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Arts, entertainment, and cultural opportunities (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Community events and festivals (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
Local government (5)	<input type="radio"/>				
Public spaces (6)	<input type="radio"/>				
Opportunities for safe biking and walking (7)	<input type="radio"/>				
Parks and recreation opportunities (8)	<input type="radio"/>				
Public transportation (9)	<input type="radio"/>				
Public schools (10)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q156 CITY SERVICES

Q321 Below are changes, initiatives, and programs that may or may not have developed and taken place in your community in the past 4 years. Please indicate how aware you are of these changes using the scale below.

	Have taken advantage of (3)	Aware of, but have not taken advantage of (11)	Unsure if this has happened or if I have taken advantage of this (12)	Unaware that this has happened in my community (14)	Certain that this has not happened in my community (15)
Rebate Program for energy efficient appliances (Efficiency Smart) (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The enhancement of services to improve the energy efficiency in homes (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Development of a cooperative to add solar energy to home rooftops (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Wider selection of locally grown foods in farmer's market (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Expansion/creation of community gardening (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Addition of bike lanes (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consolidation of recycling into single stream (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Updating recycling bins with bigger ones (12)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Expansion of recyclable items to include paper and cardboard (13)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q323 Below are changes, initiatives, and programs that may or may not have developed and taken place in your community in the past 4 years. Please indicate how aware you are of these changes using the scale below.

	Aware that this has happened in my community (11)	Unsure if this has happened in my community (12)	Unaware that this has happened in my community (14)	Certain that this has not happened in my community (15)
Competitions to reduce electricity and water usage in public schools (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Debates over how to spend dollars from renewable energy credits (REC debate) (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Significant expansion of green electricity (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Development of a City Climate Action Plan (11)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q322 Are there any changes or specific programs/initiatives you were aware of that were not listed above? If so, please detail them out below.

Q120 How would you rate each of the following City of [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) services in terms of cost?

	Very Good (1)	Good (2)	Average (3)	Poor (4)	Very Poor (5)
Electric service (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Water & Sewer (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Garbage collection (3)	<input type="radio"/>				

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Q132 COMMUNITY LIFE

You will now be provided a series of statements about life in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

Q308

	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Disagree (6)	Strongly Disagree (7)
I feel like I belong in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Overall, I think \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} is a good place to raise children. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community is respectful and accepting of people who have differing religious and spiritual beliefs. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am happy to live in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community is respectful and accepting of people with different racial and ethnic backgrounds. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community is respectful and accepting of people with different political opinions. (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Despite our differences, we can commit ourselves to common community goals. (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If people in the community were planning something, I would feel that it is something WE are doing as opposed to something THEY are doing. (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Most people in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} can be trusted. (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel like a valued and valuable member of the \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community. (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

I have an understanding of how and why things happen the way they do in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). (11)

I can help make things happen or help to change things if I need to in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). (12)

I often visit with neighbors inside their homes. (13)

I often stop and talk with people in my neighborhood. (14)

I believe my neighbors would help me in an emergency. (15)

The local college and city work together to improve the community. (16)

Q160 COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION

Q59 Below is a list of activities and organizations that some people in your community participate in. Please indicate how often you participated in each of the following activities over the past year.

	Never (1)	Once a Year or Less (2)	Several Times a Year (3)	Once a Month (4)	2-3 Times a Month (5)	Once a Week (6)
Attended a public meeting or council meeting (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Worked with other community members to solve a community problem (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Attended church or religious services or activities of faith-based organization (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participated in a PTA/PTO or other K-12 school-based organization (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Voted in local elections (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q163 QUALITY OF LIFE AND COST OF LIVING

Q19 Below are some questions about the overall quality of life and cost of living in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$.

	Very Good (1)	Good (2)	Average (3)	Bad (4)	Very Bad (5)
Overall, how would you rate $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ as a place for shopping, recreation, working, and living? (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Overall, how would you rate the cost of living in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$? (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Compared to the cost of living in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ two years ago, how would you rate the cost of living in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ now? (4)	<input type="radio"/>				

End of Block: Section I - Community Satisfaction

Start of Block: Section II - Recycling, Energy and Water Use

Q54 Overall how motivated are you to do each of the following activities?

	Highly Motivated (1)	Motivated (2)	Somewhat motivated (3)	Only slightly motivated (4)	Not at all motivated (5)
Conserve energy (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bike or walk for transportation (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reduce water use (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improve water quality (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Purchase local foods (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Recycle (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Compost (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Shop locally (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bike, walk or run for exercise (11)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q151 **RECYCLING** The following statements are about recycling in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

Q303

	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Disagree (6)	Strongly disagree (7)
There are resources in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} to help me recycle. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I know the items that can be put in our recycling container for curbside pickup. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is easy for me to be consistent about recycling in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} . (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q204 How often do you think residents of [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) recycle?

- Very Often (1)
 - Often (2)
 - Sometimes (3)
 - Rarely (4)
 - Never (5)
-

Q261 How often do you recycle?

- Always (1)
- Very often (2)
- Often (3)
- Sometimes (4)
- Rarely or Never (5)

Display This Question:

If Q261 = Rarely or Never

Q319 What prevents you from recycling?

Q177 What do you do with yard waste materials?

- Compost in my own yard (1)
- Put curbside for city pick-up (2)
- Bag it for trash pick-up (3)
- I do not have a yard (4)

Q297 Do you compost (food scraps)?

- Yes (4)
 - No (5)
-

Q298 There are resources in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) to help me compost.

- Strongly Agree (1)
 - Agree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (4)
 - Disagree (6)
 - Strongly Disagree (7)
-

Q152 ENERGY USE The following statements are about energy use in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

Q304

	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)	Disagree (4)	Strongly Disagree (5)
I feel the \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community supports efforts to reduce household energy consumption and save on household energy costs. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There are programs and resources in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} to help me reduce my household energy consumption and costs. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is someone in my community who can give advice or support to help reduce my household energy consumption and costs. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believe that as a community we can work together to reduce our total energy consumption. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I often think about energy consumption when I turn a light or appliance on or off. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I consciously make decisions to minimize my energy use. (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I consciously make decisions to minimize other people's energy use in my household. (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have relatively little ability to influence energy consumption in my household. (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have a good sense of the different sources of electricity generation used to provide \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} residents with electrical power. (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel aware of total electricity use by the whole \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community. (11)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The amount of electricity I use has an important impact on the natural environment. (12)

Q202 How often do you think residents of $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ try to conserve energy?

- Very Often (1)
 - Often (2)
 - Sometimes (3)
 - Rarely (4)
 - Never (5)
-

Q309 How often do you try to conserve energy?

- Very Often (1)
 - Often (2)
 - Sometimes (3)
 - Rarely (4)
 - Never (5)
-

Display This Question:

If Q309 = Never

Or Q309 = Rarely

Q318 What prevents you from conserving energy?

Q11 During a typical winter, at what temperature in degrees Fahrenheit do you generally keep the thermostat when at home?

- 50-60 F (9)
- 60-65 F (1)
- 66-67 F (2)
- 68-69 F (3)
- 70-71 F (4)
- 72-73 F (5)
- 74-75 F (6)
- 76-77 F (7)
- 78 F or Higher (8)

Q192 Do you have and use a programmable thermostat?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)
- Not sure (3)

Display This Question:

If Q192 = Yes

Q266 Do you use the programmable thermostat to adjust the temperature of your home when you are away from home or asleep?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)
- Sometimes (3)

Q62 Below are some types of improvements or actions some people take to reduce consumption of energy in their home. Please indicate whether you or someone else in your household or a landlord have taken these steps in the past 5 years.

	Yes (1)	No (2)	Not Sure (3)
Installed energy-efficient windows (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Installed new insulation to reduce heating costs (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Installed energy-efficient appliances (e.g., Energy Star) (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other home improvements to reduce energy consumption (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q168 What percentage of the light bulbs in your home are energy-efficient (compact fluorescent or LED)?

- 0% (1)
 - Less than 25% (6)
 - Between 25% - 50% (2)
 - Between 50% - 75% (3)
 - Over 75% (4)
-

Q173 How often do you use line-drying instead of an electric or gas clothes dryer?

- Always (1)
 - Very Often (2)
 - Often (3)
 - Sometimes (4)
 - Rarely or Never (5)
-

Q193 Have you installed timers or motion sensors on lights or other automatic devices to reduce electricity use and costs?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - Not Sure (3)
-

Q71 Do you have air conditioning where you live?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Display This Question:

If Q71 = Yes

Q70 In the summer months, how warm would it have to be inside your home based on the thermostat for you to turn on the air conditioning?

- 60-64 F (13)
- 65-67 F (1)
- 68-69 F (2)
- 70-71 F (3)
- 72-73 F (4)
- 74-75 F (5)
- 76-77 F (6)
- 78-79 F (7)
- 80-81F (8)
- 82-83F (9)
- 84-85F (10)
- > 85F (11)
- I would not use air conditioning regardless of temperature (12)

Display This Question:

If Q71 = Yes

Q88 About how many days during a typical summer do you use air conditioning?

- Every day (1)
 - Most days (2)
 - Some days (4)
 - Only when it is extremely hot (5)
 - Not at all (6)
-

Q320 Which if any of the following renewable energy sources have you installed in your home?

- Solar (eg photovoltaics, solar panels) (1)
 - Geothermal (2)
 - Wind (3)
 - Biomass (eg wood stove) (4)
 - Other (5) _____
 - None of these renewable energy sources have been installed in my home (6)
-

Q21 How important is it that each of the following types of buildings are renovated to reduce energy use and waste?

	Extremely Important (1)	Very Important (2)	Somewhat Important (3)	Not Very Important (4)	Not At All Important (5)
The public library (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The public schools (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Government buildings such as City Hall (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
College buildings (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Local businesses (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Individual homes (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q253 **WATER USE & WATER QUALITY** The following statements are about water use, the environment and water quality in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

Q305

	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Disagree (6)	Strongly disagree (7)
The \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community supports efforts to preserve water quality in creek, rivers, and lakes. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believe that as a community we can work together to improve water quality in creeks, rivers, and lakes. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I often think about water consumption when I am taking a shower, flushing the toilet, washing my hands or using water in other ways. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I consciously make decisions to minimize the amount of water I use. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I consciously make decisions to minimize the amount of water other people in my household use. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have relatively little ability to influence local water quality in creeks, rivers, and lakes. (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have relatively little ability to influence water consumption in my household. (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My water use has an important impact on the environment. (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have a good sense of the natural body of water that provides tap water for Oberlin residents and how water is stored, treated and delivered to my home. (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel aware of total water use by the whole \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community. (11)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The amount of water I use has an important impact on the natural	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

environment. (10)

|

Q325 The following statements are about water use, the environment and water quality in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). Please indicate how much you think about each statement.

	Always (1)	Often (2)	Sometimes (4)	Infrequently (6)	Never (7)
I think about where my water is coming from when I turn on the faucet or hose, take a shower or turn on appliances that use water. (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
I think about the water lines that run through the city to my home. (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
I think about where my water is going once I've used it. (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
I think about the environmental resources necessary to treat drinking water and to treat waste water. (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
I think about water cleanliness and pollution in local creeks, streams, rivers and bodies of water. (13)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q315 How often do you think residents of $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ try to conserve water?

- Very Often (1)
 - Often (2)
 - Sometimes (3)
 - Rarely (4)
 - Never (5)
-

Q316 How often do you try to conserve water?

- Very Often (1)
 - Often (2)
 - Sometimes (3)
 - Rarely (4)
 - Never (5)
-

Display This Question:

If Q316 = Never

Or Q316 = Rarely

Q317 What prevents you from conserving water?

Q174 Have you or someone else installed a low-flow toilet in your home?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)
- Not Sure (3)

Q175 Have you or someone else installed a low-flow showerhead in your home?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)
- Not Sure (3)

Q176 Do you have a rain barrel for collecting water run-off from your gutters?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)
- Not Sure (3)

Q300 How often do you shower?

- 3 or more times a day (1)
 - Twice a day (2)
 - Once a day (3)
 - every other day (4)
 - every 3 days or less often (5)
-

Q12 When taking a shower, about how long do you usually take in minutes?

- Less than 5 minutes (1)
- 5 - 10 minutes (2)
- 10 - 15 minutes (3)
- 15 - 20 minutes (4)
- More than 20 minutes (5)

End of Block: Section II - Recycling, Energy and Water Use

Start of Block: Section III - Transportation Options

Q254 **TRANSPORTATION OPTIONS** The following statements are about transportation options in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) including public transit, walking and biking. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

Q306

	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Disagree (6)	Strongly disagree (7)
The \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community supports efforts to bicycle and walk. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believe that as a community we can work together to reduce automobile use in town. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is easy for me to bike or walk to places I would like to go in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} . (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is easy for me to use public transportation to go places I would like to go. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q299 If public transportation were available in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) how likely would you be to use it?

- Very Likely (4)
 - Likely (5)
 - Unsure (6)
 - Unlikely (7)
 - Very Unlikely (8)
-

Q205 How often do you think residents of [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) ride bikes to get around town?

- Very Often (1)
 - Often (2)
 - Sometimes (3)
 - Rarely (4)
 - Never (5)
-

Q311 How often do you think residents of [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) walk to get around town?

- Very Often (1)
 - Often (2)
 - Sometimes (3)
 - Rarely (4)
 - Never (5)
-

Q295 How often do you bike to get around town?

- Very Often (5)
 - Often (6)
 - Sometimes (7)
 - Rarely (8)
 - Never (9)
-

Q312 How often do you walk to get around town?

- Very Often (5)
- Often (6)
- Sometimes (7)
- Rarely (8)
- Never (9)

Display This Question:

If Q295 = Never

Or Q295 = Rarely

Q310 What prevents you from biking to get around town?

Display This Question:

If Q312 = Never

Or Q312 = Rarely

Q313 What prevents you from walking to get around town?

End of Block: Section III - Transportation Options

Start of Block: Section IV - Local Food and Food Access and the Economy

Q122 ACCESS TO FOOD & LOCAL FOOD PRODUCTION

The following

questions are about the availability of food and your opinions about locally produced foods.

Q294 Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Disagree (6)	Strongly disagree (7)
I can easily find information on farmers' markets and where to find locally grown foods in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find that locally grown foods tend to be more expensive than non-locally grown foods. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can easily purchase fresh fruits and vegetables in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Q268 Roughly what percentage of the food you eat do you grow yourself?

- 0% (5)
 - Less than 25% (1)
 - Between 25% - 50% (2)
 - Between 50% - 75% (3)
 - Over 75% (4)
-

Q301 I obtain most of my food from

- Larger chain stores (Walmart, Drugmart, etc) (1)
 - Farmers' market (2)
 - Food pantry/Community Service Center (3)
 - Local Grocery Store (4)
 - I grow most of my own food (5)
 - Other (6)
-

Page Break

Q270 Do you preserve any food to eat at a later time?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Page Break

Q251 How many of the meals that you eat at home use unprocessed (e.g. fresh produce) or minimally processed (e.g. pasta) ingredients?

- All meals (1)
- Most Meals (2)
- Some Meals (3)
- A Few Meals (4)
- Almost No Meals (5)

Page Break

Q15 When shopping for food, please indicate how important each of the following factors is in determining what you purchase.

	Extremely Important (1)	Very Important (2)	Somewhat Important (3)	Not That Important (4)	Not At All Important (5)
Whether the food is locally grown or produced. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Whether the food is organic. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Whether the food is unprocessed. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
That meat is raised in a humane manner (leave blank if you don't eat meat). (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Whether the food item is the most affordable of its kind. (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Section IV - Local Food and Food Access and the Economy

Start of Block: Section V - Local Economy and Development

Q252 LOCAL ECONOMY & BUSINESS CLIMATE The following statements are about the local business climate in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

Q307

	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Disagree (6)	Strongly disagree (7)
The \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community supports our local businesses by shopping locally. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
 \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} businesses are an important source of jobs for local residents. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
As a community we can work together to improve the local economy regardless of what happens elsewhere. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
 \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} offers the types of restaurants that I prefer. (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
 \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} offers the types of businesses and shops that I prefer. (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
 I believe \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} can be a destination for regional tourism. (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q302 Below are a series of statements about business entrepreneurship. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements.

	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (4)	Neither agree nor disagree (6)	Disagree (7)	Strongly Disagree (8)
If I wanted to start a business in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} I would feel supported. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that I have resources that I would need to start a business in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} could sustain more businesses. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q289 How do you feel the local college positively or negatively impacts the community in each of the following areas?

	Negatively (1)	Somewhat Negatively (2)	Neutral (3)	Somewhat Positively (4)	Positively (5)
Local businesses (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Local schools (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
City government and politics (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Community safety (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Community non-profit organizations (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Arts, culture and events (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Downtown and other public spaces (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Neighborhood quality of life (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Section V - Local Economy and Development

Start of Block: Section VII - Personal Behavior and Demographic Characteristics

Q258 DEMOGRAPHICS The following demographic questions are for statistical purposes only and to help assure that the responses we receive are representative of the general population.

Q39 What is your age (in years)?

Q40 Gender:

Q42 Are you either Hispanic or Latino?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Q41 What categories describe you? (Click all that apply)

American Indian or Alaska Native (1)

Asian (2)

Black or African American (3)

Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander (4)

White (5)

Middle Eastern/North African (8)

Other (7) _____

Q74 How long have you lived in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$?

- < 1 year (1)
 - 1-2 years (2)
 - 3-4 years (3)
 - 5-10 years (4)
 - > 10 years (5)
-

Q96 What would you estimate as your total household income per year?

- < \$20,000 (1)
 - \$20,000 - \$39,999 (2)
 - \$40,000 - \$59,999 (3)
 - \$60,000 - \$79,999 (4)
 - \$80,000 - \$99,999 (5)
 - \$100,000 + (6)
 - I do not wish to share this information (7)
-

Q43 Please tell us a little about who lives in your home. For each of the following, please indicate how many people in each category live in your home.

Older Adults > Age 70 (1)

Adults ages 30-70 (2) _____

Young adults ages 18-29 (3)

Teens (12-18) (4) _____

Children ages 5-11 (5) _____

Preschoolers ages 0-4 (6)

Q47 What type of residence do you live in?

Apartment (1)

Condominium (2)

House (3)

Other (4)

Display This Question:

If Q47 = House

Or Q47 = Condominium

Or Q47 = Other

Q52 Do you (or other people who live with you) own your home?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Q63 Do you own or lease a motor vehicle or have regular access to a motor vehicle?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Skip To: Q67 If Q63 = No

Q65 For the vehicle you drive the most often, what would you estimate as the vehicle's typical miles per gallon?

- < 10 MPG (1)
 - 10-15 MPG (2)
 - 16-20 MPG (3)
 - 21-25 MPG (4)
 - 26-30 MPG (5)
 - 31-35 MPG (6)
 - 36-40 MPG (7)
 - > 40 MPG (8)
-

Q66 In a typical year, about how many miles do you drive?

- Less than 5,000 (1)
 - 5,000-7,499 (2)
 - 7,500-9,999 (3)
 - 10,000-12,499 (4)
 - 12,500-14,999 (5)
 - 15,000-19,999 (6)
 - 20,000-24,999 (7)
 - 25,000-29,999 (8)
 - 30,000 or more (9)
-

Q67 Do you currently work either full-time or part-time?

- Yes, I work full-time (1)
- Yes, I work part-time (2)
- No, I am not currently working (3)

Skip To: Q73 If Q67 = No, I am not currently working

Q68 How many miles do you travel to work in each direction? That is, how far is it in miles from where you live from where you work?

- 0 to 1 Mile (1)
- 2-3 Miles (2)
- 4-5 Miles (3)
- 6-10 Miles (4)
- 11-15 Miles (5)
- 16-20 Miles (6)
- 21-25 Miles (7)
- 26-30 Miles (8)
- 31-35 Miles (9)
- 36-40 Miles (10)
- > 40 Miles (11)

Display This Question:

If Q68 = > 40 Miles

Q69 How many miles do you typically drive to work each way?

Q72 In the past 7 days, what was your primary form of transportation to get to and from work?

- Drove alone (1)
 - Carpool (2)
 - Public transit (3)
 - Walking (4)
 - Biking (5)
-

Q292 How often are you required or do you feel obligated to work more than 40 hours per week at your primary job?

- Every week (1)
 - Often (2)
 - Sometimes (3)
 - Rarely (4)
 - Never (5)
-

Q73 In the past 7 days, what was your primary form of transportation for all trips including shopping, running errands and work?

- Drove alone (1)
 - Carpool (2)
 - Public transit (3)
 - Walking (4)
 - Biking (5)
-

Q60 Below is a list of local sources of information some people use to get information about things happening in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). For each source listed below, please indicate how often you get information from that source about [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#).

	Never (1)	Once a Year or Less (2)	Several Times a Year (3)	Once a Month (4)	2-3 Times a Month (5)	Once a Week (6)	2-3 Times a Week (7)	4-6 Times a Week (8)	Daily (9)
Local-access cable television channel (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Local newspaper (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Community newsletters (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
School newsletters (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Local college publications (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bulletin boards in local businesses and public buildings (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electronic or digital display boards (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Local community organization websites (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
City website (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

College
website (10)

Display This Question:
If Q260 = Oberlin

Q79 Before concluding this survey, we want to make sure that all residents of the City of [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) are equally represented in this survey. Shown below is a Google map of City of [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) where the pin marked "A" marks the geographic center of town. Please indicate on the map below the approximate location of where you live within [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) by clicking on that location on the map below. If you prefer not to indicate approximately where you live or cannot find your location on the map, simply select a location or landmark on the map which is in the general direction of where you live relative to the pin marked "A".

Display This Question:

If Q260 = Berea

Q286 Before concluding this survey, we want to make sure that all residents of the City of $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ are equally represented in this survey. Shown below is a Google map of City of $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ where the pin marked "A" marks the geographic center of town. Please indicate on the map below the approximate location of where you live within $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ by clicking on that location on the map below. If you prefer not to indicate approximately where you live or cannot find your location on the map, simply select a location or landmark on the map which is in the general direction of where you live relative to the pin marked "A".

Q314 This survey is part of a longitudinal study. If you are willing to be contacted again in the future for a followup survey, please enter your email address in the text box below. Your email address will not be stored with your responses and providing your email address does not obligate you to participate in other studies. We will not share your email address with third parties and will only use it to invite you to take the followup survey.

Display This Question:

If If Please enter the RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the ... Text Response Is Equal to A2012109*

Or Or Please enter the RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the ... Text Response Is Equal to B2012109*

Or Or Please enter the RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the ... Text Response Is Equal to a2012109*

Or Or Please enter the RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the ... Text Response Is Equal to b2012109*

Q293 Based on the RESPONDENT ID you provided, you entered a general code for your city based on a reminder card delivered to your address. To help avoid any possible duplicate responses in the survey results, please do one of the following: 1) Enter the numeric portion of your street address in the box below. For example, if you live at 1005 Maple St., you would enter "1005". If you live at 3 Maple Street you would just enter the number "3" in the box below. OR 2) If you have the original letter inviting you to participate with your original RESPONDENT ID, please enter that RESPONDENT ID (e.g. "A101001") in the box below.

End of Block: Section VII - Personal Behavior and Demographic Characteristics
